

Methodology for Calculating Shutdown Dose Rates in MSRR Structural Components Using SCALE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a methodology and preliminary results to calculate activation dose rates for a representative model of the upper containment region of the Molten Salt Research Reactor (MSRR). This region contains the steel components with trace cobalt impurities that undergo activation through neutron capture. We use the SCALE 6.3.2 computational suite to examine gamma doses resulting from neutron activation in stainless steel components above the gamma plate. Our approach includes discretization of activated components in the gamma shield, followed by calculating neutron flux, then modeling isotopic depletion, followed by a full gamma transport analysis. Preliminary results show convergence in dose estimation with increased discretization resolution, which has useful implications for maintenance planning and reactor safety evaluations.

Keywords: Shutdown dose calculation, Neutron activation, Gamma dose, Molten Salt Research Reactor, Structural Steel Activation, SCALE 6.3.2

1. MSRR: BACKGROUND

The Molten Salt Research Reactor (MSRR) is a university-scale research reactor currently under construction at Abilene Christian University in Texas, USA. This reactor, described in detail previously [1], employs molten salt fuels similar to ORNL's historic Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE). The MSRR upper containment regions include structural components such as the steel gamma shielding plates above the reactor enclosure. These stainless-steel (SS-316H) components inherently contain trace cobalt impurities that influence neutron activation and result in gamma radiation post reactor shutdown.

Activation dose calculations within the reactor containment regions serve dual purposes: first, they ensure compliance with radiological safety limits set by the regulatory agencies, and second, they inform practical decisions for reactor maintenance, planning, and operations. This paper discusses the methodology and preliminary activation dose analysis results for the MSRR upper containment region using representative geometric models. The workflow described in this paper is orchestrated by the Natura Nuclear Code (NaNuC) [2], a Python-based automation framework developed to streamline multi-step SCALE analyses using SCALE 6.3.2 [3]. NaNuC handles input-deck modification, volume and flux extraction, automatic generation of ORIGEN irradiation cases, and post-processing of MAVRIC/Monaco mesh tallies. By scripting the data flow between SCALE sequences, NaNuC reduces manual intervention, minimizes transcription errors, and enables rapid parametric sweeps over burn/decay scenarios and discretization resolutions. We also automate the creation of discretized subdivisions of the gamma shield to allow for more spatially accurate flux and activation modeling. Predicting post-shutdown neutron induced gamma dose rates is essential for maintenance planning, regulatory compliance, and personnel safety.

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2. ACTIVATION DOSE ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

Neutron irradiation of structural reactor components results in activation, a process where stable nuclei capture neutrons and transmute into radioactive isotopes. These radioactive isotopes subsequently emit gamma radiation, leading to potential radiation hazards post reactor shutdown. Accurate prediction of shutdown dose rates (SDRs) is essential for safety assessment, maintenance planning, and regulatory compliance in nuclear reactor facilities. The structural components in Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) are commonly composed of stainless steel alloys such as SS-316H, which undergo activation predominantly through neutron capture by impurities such as (^{59}Co), producing (^{60}Co), a gamma emitter with a half-life of 5.27 years.

Our computational methodology integrates multiple SCALE 6.3.2 modules to estimate neutron-induced activation doses post-shutdown. Furthermore, we utilize SCALE's "Fulcrum": the Graphical User Interface for geometry visualization and verification. Each analysis step involves a specific modeling tool and outputs that feeds into the consequent step.

2.1. Rigorous Two-Step (R2S) Methodology in SCALE

The Rigorous Two-Step (R2S) methodology is the standard computational approach to calculate SDRs in nuclear systems. The "two step" part of the name implies that neutron and photon transport steps are done separately, as opposed to the Direct One Step (D1S) method, which performs both transport calculations simultaneously [4]. Our computational methodology follows the R2S approach, integrating multiple SCALE 6.3.2 modules and Python automation. Below are the steps as illustrated in Figure 1:

1. Modify the nominal MSRR input deck

Modify a nominal MSRR input deck to incorporate the specific materials and discretized sub-volumes. This requires adding new materials into the model, defining their compositions, adding new cells corresponding to the enclosure top and some "n" number of axial layers of the steel gamma plate. Figure 2 visually demonstrates this.

2. Calculate region volumes using SHIFT

SCALE/SHIFT sequence is a general-purpose, continuous-energy, parallel Monte Carlo neutron and photon transport code included in the SCALE software suite. This step is essential in order to normalize neutron flux and source distributions.

3. Use TRITON to calculate neutron flux

SCALE/TRITON sequence simulates neutron transport and tracks isotopic evolution of depletion, or, as it is in our case, activation of steel, over time. Here, "F33" output files are generated, which contain detailed flux tally data and energy-dependent neutron flux spectrum.

4. Extract volume and flux data

We have developed a Python script that extracts the volumes of relevant regions from SHIFT, gets the corresponding total scalar fluxes and one-group cross-section libraries (F33 files) from TRITON, and automatically generates ORIGEN input files.

5. Use ORIGEN to model depletion and activation

Our automated scripts then feed the neutron flux data into SCALE/ORIGEN sequence to simulate isotopic compositions, activities, decay heat, and gamma spectra. ORIGEN will irradiate the region containing SS-316H steel using the specified neutron flux for a set irradiation time, and then let it decay for a set decay time. The results are saved in "F71" files, one for each material depleted by ORIGEN. The F71 files contain the total number of nuclides for each segment of the activated steel, and are used as gamma sources in the MAVRIC sequence.

6. Use F71 files in MAVRIC/Monaco to compute radiation doses in gamma shield

MAVRIC/Monaco sequence transports gammas and computes radiation doses in the upper encl-

sure and gamma shield.

7. Automated Scripts to Plot Fluxes

Flux distribution plots are generated to visualize how the neutron flux varies with depth inside the gamma shield.

8. Convert dose mesh to VTK format.

The MAVRIC/Monaco gamma transport calculation generates SCALE's "3dmap" binary mesh tallies. Since Monaco is a single-threaded code, we get parallel performance by running multiple Monaco simulations with different seeds, and average the resulting meshes. This merged mesh tally is then converted to a VTK format, which can be read by standard tools. We use a Python VTK framework PyVista [5] for post-processing. This step creates detailed 3D visualization maps of the dose distributions that allow us to see how radiation levels vary across different regions of the gamma shield.

9. Extract dose in cylindrical layers and plot the average dose.

The dose values are averaged as a function of z-position within the barrel section of the upper enclosure, and plotted to observe convergence among the runs with various subdivisions. This allows us to judge whether the mesh refinement converged and better understand how shielding thickness affects radiation penetration and dose rates.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the R2S activation dose analysis methodology.

3. GEOMETRIC DISCRETIZATION AND REPRESENTATIVE MODEL

A representative geometric discretization model of the MSRR upper containment enclosure was developed, focusing on accurately resolving neutron activation gradients and resulting gamma dose distributions. The representative model incorporates a gamma shielding plate with a thickness of 12.7cm. The gamma shield and adjacent structural components were discretized into multiple axial layers to enhance resolution, capturing activation profiles and photon flux distributions effectively.

The geometric discretization employs a structured mesh with a 3×3 mesh in the XY axis (seen in Figure 2) and 10 axial mesh cells, resulting in 90 distinct volumetric cells, each assigned a unique mixture number within the SCALE model. The part of the containment barrel above the gamma plate was discretized axially into 5 equidistant layers to account for flux variation. This spatial discretization allows

the transport solver to capture both XY and depth-dependent variations in neutron flux, activation distributions, and gamma dose rates. The calculation methodology includes automated data extraction and processing scripts designed to enhance efficiency, reduce manual errors, and ensure consistency and reproducibility.

Figure 2. Left: the gamma shield plate is subdivided into a $3 \times 3 \times 10$ mesh along the X, Y, and Z axes. Along the Z (axial) direction, the full 12.7cm thickness of the shield is sliced into 10 equal layers (each layer being 1.27 cm thick), capturing the depth-dependent attenuation of both neutron and gamma flux. Figure to the right: Geometric discretization of gamma plate (XY configuration, or view from top looking down). The plate is divided into a 3×3 grid – yielding nine quadrants (Q1 through Q9).

3.1. Material Profiles

Material compositions play a central role in determining shutdown dose rates because they guide the activation product buildup during operation, and spectrum of delayed radiation after shutdown. In particular, the boron concentration in B_4C , shown in mustard yellow color in Figure 2 (region below the gamma shield) matters greatly because boron is a strong neutron absorber. The ratio of boron to carbon alters the neutron capture balance and the overall effectiveness of B_4C as a shielding material: if boron content is too low, neutron absorption weakens and more activation occurs in the surrounding structural materials.

4. ACTIVATION DOSES IN UPPER CONTAINMENT ENCLOSURE

Stainless steel SS-316H inherently contains trace cobalt (^{59}Co) impurities, typically around 0.1 wt% in commercial-grade material. Neutron capture in ^{59}Co produces ^{60}Co , a gamma emitter with a half-life of ≈ 5.3 years that dominates post-shutdown dose in steel components. Our modeling assumptions, consistent with those in [1], explicitly account for this cobalt content; the full SS-316H composition used in this study is listed in Table I. Note that 1 cm of steel attenuates the ^{60}Co gamma flux by approximately 25% [6], making depth-resolved modeling essential. Each discretized steel sub-volume (Section 3) is irradiated at the local neutron flux obtained from TRITON, depleted and decayed with ORIGEN over the specified burn and cooling periods, and the resulting gamma source spectra are fed into MAVRIC/Monaco for photon transport. The activated sub-volumes thus serve as spatially distributed

Isotope	Atom Density	Isotope	Atom Density	Isotope	Atom Density
C	1.92536e-04	Cr-54	3.70329e-04	Ni-60	2.43229e-03
Si-28	5.85329e-04	Mn-55	1.38556e-03	Ni-61	1.05730e-04
Si-29	2.97351e-05	Fe-54	3.40775e-03	Ni-62	3.37113e-04
Si-30	1.96246e-05	Fe-56	5.34944e-02	Ni-64	8.58527e-05
P-31	3.73300e-05	Fe-57	1.23542e-03	Mo-92	1.55759e-04
S-32	7.13609e-07	Fe-58	1.64412e-04	Mo-94	9.73359e-05
S-33	5.63435e-09	Co-59	7.84788e-05	Mo-95	1.67675e-04
S-34	3.19280e-08	Ni-58	6.31437e-03	Mo-96	1.75901e-04
S-36	7.51247e-11	Cr-50	6.80372e-04	Mo-97	1.00816e-04
Cr-52	1.31203e-02	Cr-53	1.48774e-03	Mo-98	2.55098e-04
				Mo-100	1.01976e-04

Table I. Material Composition of SS-316H Stainless Steel. Atom density is in units of atom per barn-cm.

Isotope	50% case	100% case
B-10	0.0109308	0.0218617
B-11	0.0439979	0.0879959
C	0.0137338	0.0274676

Table II. Material composition of Boron Carbide (B_4C). Atom density is in units of atom per barn-cm.

gamma sources, enabling estimation of dose distributions throughout the upper enclosure. Figures 3a–4a present cross-sectional dose-rate maps produced by MAVRIC/Monaco for the 5 MW-year irradiation, 30-day decay case at 50% B_4C density. Figures 3a and 3b show XZ and YZ slices through the enclosure, respectively, while Figure 4a shows the XY plane at the gamma-shield surface closest to the core. To obtain scalar dose-rate profiles, we average the Monaco mesh tally over cylindrical “pancake” layers spanning the nitrogen-filled cavity above the gamma plate; the resulting depth-dependent profiles are presented in Figure 4b, which also illustrates convergence with increasing discretization resolution across the nine lateral quadrants (Q1–Q9) defined in Figure 2.

(a) XZ cross-sectional view of the photon dose (rem/hour).

(b) YZ cross-sectional view of the photon dose (rem/hour).

Figure 3. Cross-sectional dose-rate maps for the 5, MW-year irradiation, 30-day decay case at 50% B_4C density.

(a) XY (planar) view of the dose rate (rem/hour) at the surface of the gamma shield, showing the cross-section closest to the reactor core.

(b) Flux attenuation vs. shield thickness for each of the 9 quadrant mesh regions (see Figure 2) showing convergence in gamma plate.

Figure 4. Results from the 5 MW-years irradiation and 30-day decay time case with B_4C concentration 50%.

Comparison Between Different Operating Conditions

(a) Gamma dose rate [rem/h] in the enclosure after a 1-month burn and four decay times.

Discretized 3x3x10 Gamma Shield Dose vs. Axial Slice

(b) Depth-dependent gamma dose rate [rem/h] within the gamma shield for the 1-month burn, 30-day decay case.

Figure 5. Average activation gamma dose rates [rem/h] at various lengths of time.

Figure 5a shows the gamma dose rate in the upper enclosure after a one-month burn for four decay periods: 7 days (red), 1 month (blue), 3 months (green), and 1 year (orange). As expected, longer cooling times reduce the residual activity, with the 7-day curve yielding the highest dose rates and the 1-year curve the lowest. Figure 5b plots the dose rate within the gamma shield as a function of axial depth for the same one-month burn case. The three curve groups correspond to the three radial segments visible in Figure 2 (left): the center segment, which sits directly above the core and sees the shortest neutron path, consistently shows the highest dose, while the two flanking segments are roughly symmetric about the core axis and exhibit similar, lower values. Dose decreases with depth in all three segments, reflecting gamma attenuation through the 12.7 cm steel plate. The dashed red line marks the lateral mean across all nine quadrants at each depth.

To map dose sensitivity across a broader operating space, we repeated the analysis for a matrix of burn and decay durations. Figure 6 presents the results as heatmaps for two B_4C shielding densities. In both cases, dose rates increase with burn time and decrease with decay time, as expected. At 50% B_4C density (Figure 6a), the highest dose rate occurs at the longest burn and shortest decay, while the lowest corresponds to a 30-day burn followed by 1-year decay (0.00392 rem/h). Doubling the B_4C density to 100% (Figure 6b) reduces dose rates across the entire matrix, confirming the strong influence of the neutron-absorbing shield on downstream activation.

Figure 6. Average gamma dose rate [mrem/h] in the MSRR upper enclosure as a function of burn and decay duration. Each cell gives the mean dose for a specific burn–decay pair; color scales from blue (low) to red (high). For example, at the 1-year burn / 7-day decay corner, doubling the B_4C density reduces the mean dose from 120.97 mrem/h to 24.71 mrem/h, a reduction of approximately 80%.

From this visual representation, several trends become evident. Longer burn durations predictably result in higher accumulated activation levels and thus elevated post-shutdown doses. Conversely, increasing decay times substantially reduces radiation levels due to natural radioactive decay of the activated isotopes. Short burn durations, followed by a long decay duration, for example (30 day burn, 1-year decay) yields the lowest gamma dose rate. To put these results in perspective, the annual occupational limit per NRC regulation in the U.S. for whole body exposure is 5 rem/year (5,000 mrem/year). If we take 1-year burn duration and 30-day decay in the more conservative case, our average gamma dose is about 100.56 mrem/hr (≈ 0.1 rem/hr). This means if a worker spends just one hour in a region with this amount of radiation, their exposure would be 0.1 rem, and given an 8-hour workday, this would be $0.1 \text{ rem/hr} \times 8 \text{ hours} \approx 0.8 \text{ rem}$. Comparing this to annual occupational limits, a full 8-hour workday in this type of radiation environment exposes the worker to $\approx 16\%$ of the annual limit in one day. Of course, this falls off drastically as we increase the decay time. This quick back-of-the-envelope calculation implies that short-term (minutes to hours) work may be possible with careful planning, shielding, and protective measures depending on the burn and decay time periods. Note that our values represent a volume-averaged dose; local rates near the gamma-plate surface will be higher.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The primary objectives achieved in this study were: (i) create an automated workflow to estimate gamma dose rates due to neutron activation in structural stainless steel (SS-316H) in a representative model of the MSRR; and (ii) evaluate the sensitivity of gamma dose with spatial discretizations of the gamma shield.

Our methodology involves the use of automated data extraction and processing scripts, which reduce manual errors and ensure better efficiency, consistency, and reproducibility across multiple parameter studies. This finding emphasizes the importance of spatial resolution in neutron flux modeling for accurate activation dose prediction. However, finer discretization also increases statistical noise in Monte Carlo transport simulations. Hence, an optimal balance between spatial resolution and computational resources must be carefully chosen for practical reactor design assessments.

Several simplifying assumptions adopted here align closely with those outlined by Chvála et al. [1]. Specifically, uniform activation of structural materials and simplified cobalt impurity modeling potentially underestimates the true complexity of activation distribution. Furthermore, fuel salt circulation and dynamic neutron flux changes that are common in Molten Salt Reactors are not explicitly modeled in our current stationary approach. Future studies may address these simplifications by incorporating more detailed modeling of reactor dynamics and material heterogeneity. A key assumption in this approach is that neutron activation is treated as spatially uniform within each discretized sub-volume.

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